

Exploring Lime Mortar Microstructure: Investigating the Impact of Mixed-in Additives and their Role in Salt Efflorescence Inhibition

Dulce Elizabeth Valdez Madrid^{1,2*}, *Chandra Widyananda Winardhi*¹, *Nele De Belie*², and *Veerle Cnudde*^{1,3}

¹Department of Geology, Ghent University, Krijgslaan 281/Building S8, B-9000, Belgium

²Department of Structural Engineering and Building Materials, Magnel-Vandepitte Laboratory, Ghent University, Zwijnaarde 60, B-9052, Belgium

³Department of Earth Sciences, Utrecht University, Princetonlaan 8a, 3584, The Netherlands

Abstract. This study presents the analysis of the crystallization impact in four lime-based mortar mixtures in order to determine the extent of decay during salt crystallization, affected by the use of additives and change in microstructure. For this purpose, non-destructive micro-computed tomography was used to monitor salt crystallization in lime mortar cores. This technique allowed tracking of salt precipitation after accelerated weathering steps and further enabled the localization of damage due to salt crystallization in both time and space. Results indicate that the internal 3D microstructure of the lime mortars is greatly influenced by the type and the amount of additive used. Polyacrylic acid (PAA) acted as a superplasticizer and air entrainer in the mixture, resulting in the formation of larger air voids, which led to a decrease in compressive strength. Mobilization of salts within the mortar matrix was observed, causing accumulation and cracking of the mortar wall towards the end of the weathering experiment.

1 Introduction

The microstructure of building materials plays a significant role during weathering and determines their decay extent. This decay is often caused by soluble salts that migrate into the structures and react due to the changing environmental conditions. As a preventive measure, additives and surface treatments in aqueous solutions have been used to inhibit or delay the damage caused by salt crystallization [1–6]. Nevertheless, studies on mixed-in crystallization inhibitors during the preparation of the material and their effect on the microstructure pre- and post-weathering are still limited.

To provide a better understanding of the mortar properties and assess the effects of mixed-in additives on their microstructure, X-ray micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) was utilized. Micro-CT imaging allowed to enhance the contrast between the lime-based

* Corresponding author: dulceelizabeth.valdezmadrid@ugent.be

These proceedings are published with the support of EuLA.

binders and the resulting efflorescence during accelerated weathering, as it is often challenging to assess the surface damage solely by visual inspection [7]. Benefiting from its non-destructive nature, micro-CT can be applied to monitor the specimens during the accelerated weathering process induced by salt crystallization, which promote decay.

2 Materials

Standard prisms (40 x 40 x 160 mm³) and cylinders of 25 mm diameter and 25 mm high were prepared of four lime-based mortar mixtures (Table 1). CL90-S hydrated lime was used for the binder, and CEN-Standard sand (size fraction between 0.08 and 2.00 mm [8]) for the aggregates was mixed in accordance with EN 1015-11 [9]. A binder-to-aggregate ratio of 1:3 by volume was used. Nitrilotri (methyl phosphonic acid) (ATMP) and poly (acrylic acid sodium salt) with 5100 (PAA5) and 2100 molecular weight (Mw) (PAA2) were added as salt crystallization inhibitors during the mixing process using 1000 ppm (of the total dry mass of binder and aggregates). The water-to-binder ratios (W/b) were adjusted to achieve a flow of 165 ± 10 mm, in accordance with EN 1015-3 [10]. The samples were then cured for 7 days at 20 ± 3 °C, $95 \pm 5\%$ RH and 16 months at 20 ± 3 °C, $65 \pm 5\%$ RH to ensure full carbonation of the specimens prior to testing. A reference mortar mixture without additives was prepared under identical conditions.

Table 1. Composition of the mortar mixtures analyzed and formula of the additives used.

Samples ID	Additive type*	Additive chemical formula	Additive (g)	Lime (g)	Sand (g)	W/b ratio (by volume)
REF	-	-	-	113	1350	0.80
ATMP-1000	ATMP	$N[CH_2PO(OH)_2]_3$	1.463	113	1350	0.80
PAA5-1000	PAA5	$C_3H_3NaO_2$	1.463	113	1350	0.75
PAA2-1000	PAA2	$C_3H_3NaO_2$	1.463	113	1350	0.70

*1000 parts per million were added with respect to the total lime + sand dry mass.

3 Methods

3.1 Structural characterization

Compressive strength of the mortars with additives was assessed after 16 months of curing [9]. Flexural strength was below the detection limit of the testing equipment. To ensure full carbonation of the specimens was achieved, phenolphthalein was sprayed on the freshly exposed surfaces of the mortar prisms.

3.2 X-ray micro-computed tomography

Scanning of the mortar cylinders was carried out to investigate the changes in the microstructure by the use of additives and their impact during weathering by using CoreTOM (TESCAN) at UGCT facilities from Ghent University (Belgium). The scanning was performed at 28 μ m voxel size with 120 kV accelerating voltage, 28 W power, 600 ms exposure time and a 1 mm aluminum filter. The filter was utilized to reduce possible artefacts in the reconstructed data. The scanning resulted in a total of 2142 projection images, which were reconstructed using Panthera software (TESCAN). The samples were scanned prior and after treatment.

The image processing of the reconstructed data was performed using Avizo 3D 2022 (ThermoFisher). A volume edit module was utilized to remove the parafilm coating from the samples and the surrounding background. A non-local means filter module was then applied to reduce the noise of the images. Only the scans before treatment were used to analyze the microstructure.

The microstructural analysis was performed by an interactive thresholding module to segment the air voids. Subsequently, a separate objects module was applied to isolate individual features for particle quantification and to assign shape and volume attributes. Objects below 55 microns were filtered out with an assumption that objects that were equal or below the scanning resolution were considered noise. A sieve analysis was then performed to visualize the air voids in 5 size fractions based on their equivalent diameter (<125 μm , 125-250 μm , 250-500 μm , 500-1000 μm and >1000 μm). Finally, the total porosity and the volume per size fraction were calculated.

For the weathering analysis, registration of the 3D volume was performed using the samples prior to weathering as a reference. However, due to the limitations in scanning resolution used in this study, segmenting the salt precipitation within the micropores of the mortars posed a challenge. Thus, an image subtraction module was employed to locate the occurring precipitation. Furthermore, to separate between the salt damage occurring within the samples and salt efflorescence, sub-volumes were created as a solution.

3.3 Weathering experiment

Once fully carbonated, the circumference of the mortar cylinders was sealed with parafilm and tape. Contamination with 10 % Na_2SO_4 solution was carried out by capillarity until reaching full saturation. When fully saturated, the bottom of the cylinders was sealed with parafilm and tape to promote drying through the surface. The samples were then stored in an incubator at 40 ± 1 °C and 15 ± 2 % RH for 1 week and scanned afterwards. Subsequently, 3 rewetting and drying cycles took place to mobilize the salts and promote dissolution and reprecipitation of the salts and cause accelerated decay. Every cycle consisted of rewetting with DI water by capillarity, followed by 5 hours at room conditions for equilibration, and then 6 days in the incubator to dry at 40 ± 1 °C and 15 ± 2 % RH. Scans were done every 7 days after every drying period to track the changes.

4 Results

4.1 Structural characterization

The effect on compressive strength by the use of the different salt crystallization inhibitors into the mixture was observed, and the results are reported in Table 2. During mortar preparation, W/b of ATMP-1000 mortars was not affected by the addition of ATMP. On the other hand, PAA-laden mortars resulted in a decrease in W/b and acting as plasticizer and air entrainers. ATMP-1000 and PAA5-1000 mortars display higher compressive strength than PAA2-1000 mortars. It was possible to observe that the smaller molecular weight of PAA2 had a relevant impact on the compressive strength, resulting in under half the strength of the PAA5-1000 mortars and a third of ATMP-1000 ones.

Table 2. Compressive strength (F_c) of mortars obtained after 16 months of curing [9] (The standard deviation is the result of 3 tested specimens).

Samples ID	F_c (N/mm ²) 16 months
ATMP-1000	2.7 ± 0.2
PAA5-1000	2.2 ± 0.1
PAA2-1000	0.9 ± 0.1

4.2 Micro-structural analysis

Results of the micro-structural analysis present differences in frequency, shape and size of the segmented air voids in the different samples. In Fig. 1, it can be observed that REF mortars exhibit fewer air voids compared to the rest and appear to be more rounded. On the other hand, ATMP-1000 and PAA5-1000 showed more voids above 1000 microns, with the former having voids that appear more irregular and elongated in shape. PAA2-1000 mortar, on the contrary displayed a distinct microstructure, as a decrease in air voids above 1000 microns was observed. Nevertheless, the PAA2-1000 mortar sample presented a higher concentration in the 250-500 microns and 500-1000 microns size fractions.

Fig. 1. Visualization of the mortar samples, showing a 2D cross-section (top) and a sliced 3D volume (bottom), with air voids displayed in different colors corresponding to the selected size fractions.

Particle count by size fraction is displayed in Fig. 2, and the quantification shows a relatively similar particle size distribution in REF, ATMP-1000 and PAA5-1000 mortars, which are predominantly composed of pores below 125 microns. In contrast, PAA2-1000 consists of air voids mainly within the 250-500 micron range, with a considerable decrease in pores size below 125 microns.

The total porosity percentage of the specimens and the porosity volume allocated to every size fraction are presented in Fig. 3. It is observed that the size fraction contributing to the highest pore volume in REF, ATMP-1000 and PAA5-1000 corresponds to the voids above 1000 microns. In PAA2-1000, the highest pore volume is provided by the 500-1000 microns size fraction, followed by 250-500 microns. Even though the frequency of the 55-125 microns size fraction predominates in the first 3 mortars, it represents a negligible portion of the total volume.

Fig. 2. Particle count by size fraction percentage calculated based on their equivalent diameter (EqDiameter).

Fig. 3. The calculated total porosity (%) and porosity volume (mm^3) divided by size fraction of the mortar samples.

4.3 Salt damage

Salt crystallization was visible, both on the top part of the samples and within the micropores of the samples. Due to the limitations of the scanning resolution in this study, segmentation of the salt crystallization that occurred within the samples was challenging. However, the salt crystallization contributed to the increase in the gray values of the reconstructed images. The mean gray values of each 2D slice in the z-direction were calculated (Fig. 4, left). Then the subtraction of the mean gray values between the samples prior to weathering (BW), after contamination (AC) and after weathering cycles (C1-3) provided an indication of the location of the salt crystallization within the samples (Fig. 4b). In general, it was apparent that salt precipitated over all samples, as suggested by the increase of mean gray values after weathering and after cycling. These increments were further proven by the subtracted mean gray values. It was also apparent that the salt mostly precipitated within the top part of the samples, starting from slices 100-300 (Fig. 4b).

The damage due to salt crystallization within the microstructure of the samples was also apparent, as shown by Fig. 5. This damage was mostly shown by development of voids (Fig. 5, red arrow) at the grain boundaries. Additionally, cracking of an aggregate also occurred on PAA2-1000 (Fig. 5, blue arrow). This damage suggests microstructure expansion due to salt crystallization within the micropores.

Fig. 4. (a) Mean gray values calculated from the histogram of each slice and (b) the subtraction result of the mean gray values of the samples before weathering (BW), after contamination (AC) and after cycle 3 (C3). The slice number 100 and 900 corresponds to the top and the bottom part of the scanned sample, respectively.

Fig. 5. Salt damage of the reference sample and the mortars with additives imaged with micro-CT, (a) prior to weathering, (b) after the third weathering cycle, and (c) the subtracted image showing the damage in the form of displacement or accumulation. Dark blue color denotes new voids formed, and light green color represents filling of voids due to crystallization or swelling after weathering. The red arrows indicate development of voids due to displacement, the blue arrows display cracking of an aggregate and white arrows show the salt crystallization.

5 Discussion

Clear differences were observed from the preparation of the specimens. While ATMP-1000 mortars had the same W/b as the REF mortars, PAA5-1000 and PAA2-1000 showed a decrease in W/b and compressive strength. This decrement could have been originated from its molecular weight, in which PAA acts as a plasticizer and reduces the water demand during the mortar mixing process, and its effect is enhanced when using lower Mw [1,11]. This explains why PAA5-1000 and PAA2-1000 mortars resulted in a decrease in water demand, while REF and ATMP-1000 mortars had a higher and equal W/b. Improved workability was also registered for PAA2-1000 mortars. Similar reduction in strength and W/b trend has been reported in previous research on lime mortars using air entrainers [12]. Furthermore, Balani et al. [10] have reported that the mechanical properties of the materials are affected by the length of the polymers. These authors illustrate that polymers with lower molecular weight have loosely bonded chains, whereas large polymer chains are entangled, and consequently enhance their strength. In this case, it was observed that the use of PAA2 (Mw 2100) resulted in considerably lower compressive strength than PAA5 (Mw 5100).

Results of the microstructural analysis revealed the substantial impact of PAA2 on the porosity of the mortars, raising it to almost 30% of the total volume of the specimen. The abundance of relatively big air voids in the sample (above 250 microns) also promoted the weakening of the mortar and further explains the considerable decrease in compressive

strength and compactness with respect to ATMP-1000 and PAA5-1000. This increase in porosity could have been a result of the improved workability of PAA2-1000 mortar, leading to greater air entrapment during the mixing process.

Image analysis of the micro-CT data aided in the understanding of the salt mobilization and damage propagation throughout the weathering test. Fig. 4a clearly showed in all samples an increase of the mean gray values after contamination with the salt solution, which rose slightly after three weathering cycles. This increase was given by the higher X-ray attenuation of the accumulated salts, which varies according to the salt concentration. A consistent behavior was observed in all specimens (Fig. 4b). The higher gray value differences are attributed to the final state of the samples after three weathering cycles (C3) compared to the scans taken after contamination (AC). This was mainly observed at the surface of the cylinders (slices 100-300), which was promoted by the drying from the top of the sample. REF sample showed the lesser variation, whereas ATMP-1000 resulted in the highest increase in gray values at the surface. PAA2-1000 and ATMP-1000 showed clear indications of the formation of a salt crust at the surface (Fig. 5, white arrow). On the other hand, PAA5-1000 and REF samples displayed swelling towards the surface, possibly driven by the salt precipitation pressure or the displacement due to the crack formation (Fig. 5, red arrow). However, in PAA5-1000 and PAA2-1000, a decrease in mean gray values was also observed (Fig. 4a). This could be attributed to crack development (Fig. 5, blue arrow), which created voids with lower attenuation, resulting in lower gray values. The formation of cracks could be linked to the lower strength of the PAA mortars, which is surpassed by the crystallization pressures throughout the test.

6 Conclusions

This work focused on the performance assessment of lime mortars with mixed-in additives, aided by continuous monitoring using X-ray micro-CT as a non-destructive technique. The presented results demonstrated that mixed-in additives significantly influence the performance of lime mortars, affecting water demand, workability, mechanical properties and microstructural characteristics. Mainly, PAA-modified mortars showed a reduced W/b ratio compared to the REF and ATMP-1000 due to the plasticizing effect of PAA. Additionally, PAA2-1000 mortars exhibited a substantial increase in porosity (nearly 30%) due to improved workability and increased air entrapment during fresh mortar mixing, leading to a decrease in compressive strength and density. While polymeric plasticizers like PAA improve workability and reduce water demand, they can also increase porosity and decrease compressive strength, particularly with lower Mw polymers. Thus highlighting the necessity of careful selection of these types of polymeric additives to optimize their properties for specific applications.

Micro-CT proved to be a valuable tool for non-destructive monitoring of continuous weathering cycles of mortar samples. The image analysis revealed significant insights into salt mobilization and damage propagation in lime-based mortars during weathering tests. All samples showed a consistent increase in mean gray values due to salt accumulation. In the case of PAA5-1000 and PAA2-1000 mortars, a decrease in gray values was seen, likely due to extensive crack formation caused by the combination of the salt crystallization pressures against the low-strength mortars. Salt crusts were observed in PAA2-1000 and ATMP-1000 mortars, while PAA5-1000 and REF samples displayed surface swelling, possibly due to crack-induced displacement. Furthermore, micro-CT shed light into ongoing processes within the mortar microstructure, which could facilitate the optimization process of mortar mixtures with mixed-in additives and the validation of their effectiveness as salt crystallization inhibitors.

Acknowledgements: This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Marie Skłodowska-Curie project SUBLime [Grant Agreement n° 955986].

References

1. T. Rabizadeh, D.J. Morgan, C.L. Peacock, L.G. Benning, Effectiveness of Green Additives vs Poly(acrylic acid) in Inhibiting Calcium Sulfate Dihydrate Crystallization, *Ind Eng Chem Res* 58 (2019) 1561–1569. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.8b02904>.
2. A. Kamat, B. Lubelli, E. Schlangen, Leaching behaviour of a crystallisation inhibitor in mortars, *Journal of Building Engineering* 79 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobbe.2023.107933>.
3. B. Lubelli, E. des Bouvrie, T.G. Nijland, A. Kamat, Plasters with mixed-in crystallization inhibitors: Results of a 4-year monitoring of on-site application, *J Cult Herit* 59 (2023) 10–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2022.10.016>.
4. E.M. Ruiz Agudo, *Prevención del daño debido a la cristalización de sales en el patrimonio histórico construido mediante el uso de inhibidores de la cristalización*, Editorial de la Universidad de Granada, 2007.
5. S. Gupta, K. Terheiden, L. Pel, A. Sawdy, Influence of ferrocyanide inhibitors on the transport and crystallization processes of sodium chloride in porous building materials, *Cryst Growth Des* 12 (2012) 3888–3898. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cg3002288>.
6. E. Ruiz-Agudo, C. Rodríguez-Navarro, E. Sebastián-Pardo, Sodium sulfate crystallization in the presence of phosphonates: Implications in ornamental stone conservation, *Cryst Growth Des* 6 (2006) 1575–1583. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cg050503m>.
7. S. Raneri, V. Cnudde, T. De Kock, H. Derluyn, G. Barone, P. Mazzoleni, X-ray computed micro-tomography to study the porous structure and degradation processes of a building stone from Sabucina (Sicily), *European Journal of Mineralogy* 27 (2015) 279–288. <https://doi.org/10.1127/ejm/2015/0027-2433>.
8. CEN, NBN EN 196-1: Methods of testing cement - Part 1: Determination of strength, (2016).
9. CEN, NBN EN 1015-11: Methods of test for mortar for masonry - Part 11: Determination of flexural and compressive strength of hardened mortar, 2019. www.nbn.be.
10. CEN, NBN EN 1015-3: Methods of test for mortar for masonry - Part 3: Determination of consistence of fresh mortar (by flow table), 1999. www.nbn.be (accessed May 21, 2024).
11. K. Balani, V. Verma, A. Agarwal, R. Narayan, Physical, Thermal, and Mechanical Properties of Polymers, in: *Biosurfaces*, Wiley, 2014: pp. 329–344. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118950623.appl>.
12. A. Kontić, G. Vasconcelos, C. Briceño Melendez, M. Azenha, N. Sokolović, Influence of air entrainers on the properties of hydrated lime mortars, *Constr Build Mater* 403 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.132968>.